

FAILURE BEHAVIORS OF TWO-DIMENSIONALLY RANDOM-ORIENTED
SHORT CARBON FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM
UNDER A STRESS CONCENTRATION

Yutaka Kagawa, Shin Utsunomiya, Yasuo Kogo, and Mitsuyuki Imaizumi
Materials and Electronic Device Laboratory,
Mitsubishi Electric Corporation
1-1-57, Miyashimo, Sagami-hara,
Kanagawa-ken, JAPAN

ABSTRACT

Failure behaviors of two-dimensionally random-oriented short carbon fiber reinforced composite plates under a source of stress concentration have been studied. The maximum net stress and non-linear toughness, as well as failure behavior, varied dramatically with the thickness of the composite specimen. These behaviors could be attributed to the differences of stress states in the specimen. When failure occurred under the mixed mode of plane stress and plane strain condition, crack growth phenomenon was very complex and it seemed to be necessary some modification of the conventional methods.

INTRODUCTION

Two-dimensionally random-oriented short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (2DRS-MMC) exhibits attractive properties for structural applications. Composites reinforced with fiber diameter $2 \sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ order short fibers have been developed and mechanical properties of such kinds of composite metals have been reported [1-4].

One of problems for practical use of 2DRS-MMC for load bearing components is considered to be lack of engineering design data especially under a source of stress concentration. Fracture resistance and failure behaviors of two-dimensionally random-oriented $2 \sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ order short fiber reinforced metals under a source of stress concentration, especially in the mixed mode condition of plane stress and plane strain, have not been well understood.

The purpose of this preliminary investigation was to study in-plane failure mechanism of a two-dimensionally random-oriented short carbon fiber

reinforced aluminum matrix composite under a source of stress concentration. Effects of specimen thickness on the failure behavior and mechanical properties were also examined experimentally.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Short carbon fiber (Toray:T300) of 300 μm in average length reinforced commercially pure aluminum (A1100) matrix composite was prepared by squeeze casting technique [5]. The short fiber was two-dimensionally random-oriented in the aluminum matrix. The fiber volume fraction was set to 0.3.

Plate-type specimens, in which fiber was in-plane random-oriented, were mechanically cut from as-cast ingots and polished with conventional metallographic technique. All specimen were 110 mm long, and the thickness of single-edge-notched specimens (fracture specimens) varied between 0.5 and 4 mm and that of un-notched specimens (tensile specimens) were fixed at 3 mm. The width of the tensile or fracture specimen was 12 mm. The notch width of the fracture specimens was kept constant, equal to 280 μm , and the root radius was maintained at 200 μm . The notch depth to width ratio was set to 0.5 corresponded to the notch length of 6 mm. GFRP tabs 15 mm wide, 35 mm long and 1 mm thick were bonded to the ends of the each specimens.

Tensile tests were carried out under a condition of constant displacement speed of 1.67×10^{-6} m/s at room temperature in air with a gauge length of 40 mm.

After the tests, optical and scanning electron microscopy were used to study crack growth and fracture morphology in selected specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(1) Effects of thickness on the failure behavior

A typical stress-strain curve for the tensile specimens is shown in Fig.1. The microscopic yield stress and failure stress were approximately 11 MPa and 120 MPa respectively. Young's modulus of the composites measured by strain gauge method was 45 GPa and this value was lower than that of aluminum matrix.

Load-displacement behaviors of the fracture specimen with thickness of 1.2, 2.3 and 4.0 mm are shown in Fig.2. The load-displacement behavior varied with the thickness of the fracture specimens. Non-linear deformation regions of the load versus displacement curves following after elastic deformation were recognized independently to the thickness of the fracture specimens. However, with increasing of thickness of the specimens, the non-linear load-displacement behavior tended to show more ductile fashion.

Fig.3 shows plots of net ultimate stress versus thickness of the fracture specimens. Plots of non-linear energy fracture toughness versus thickness of the fracture specimens are also shown in Fig.3. In this case,

Figure 1 Typical stress-strain curve of the composite.

Figure 2 Typical load-displacement curves for the fracture specimens (t : thickness of the specimen).

Figure 3 Plots of maximum net stress versus thickness of the fracture specimens, and non-linear energy toughness versus thickness of the fracture specimens.

Figure 4 Two types of fracture profiles for the fracture specimens (a : initial notch).

the non-linear energy fracture toughness value, \tilde{G}_C , was calculated based on non-linear energy method [6,7] and using a homogeneous isotropic stress concentration factor. The non-linear toughness parameter, \tilde{C} , was obtained as:

$$\tilde{G}_C = \tilde{C} G_C \quad (1)$$

Non-linear energy factor C in Eq.(1) was obtained from load-displacement relations for the fracture specimens. G_C in Eq.(1) at plane stress condition was calculated using Irwin's $G - K$ relation:

$$G_C = K_C^2 / E_C \quad (2)$$

where E_C is Young's modulus of the composite. K_C can be calculated using appropriate formula, which was given in Ref.[8].

As clearly shown in Fig.4, the net stress varied with the thickness of the fracture specimen and the maximum value was obtained at approximately 2 mm in thickness. The net stress decreased with increasing or decreasing thickness of the specimen from 2 mm respectively.

Although the stress state of the fracture specimens before subcritical crack growth was considered to be general yielding state, the net stresses of the fracture specimens were lower than the ultimate tensile stress of the tensile specimen. Consequently, the notch sensitivity of the fracture specimens were available under the condition of general yielding.

Non-linear energy fracture toughness also changed with thickness of the fracture specimens. At the thickness of 2 mm, maximum non-linear toughness was obtained. The non-linear energy fracture toughness versus thickness relation was quite similar to that of the ultimate net stress versus thickness relation.

(2) Crack growth under mixed mode condition

Macroscopically, The crack started from the root of a notch and extended both straightly and perpendicular to the applied load direction. Fracture profile of the fracture specimen varied with thickness of the specimens. Typical two types of fracture profiles, which were observed in this experiment, are schematically shown in Fig.4.

Up to 2 mm in thickness of the fracture specimens, fracture mode was completely slant-type, and for thickness of the specimen thicker than 2 mm, fracture profile was mixed-mode of squar and slant-type.

This results suggested that when the specimen thickness thinner than 2 mm, the stress state in the fracture specimens were essentially plane stress. On the other hand, specimen thickness thicker than 2 mm, the stress state of the fracture specimens were essentially mixed mode of plane stress and plane strain [9].

Fig.5 shows polished sections of the fracture specimen with the thickness of 3.0 mm. The sample was obtained by stopping the loading just

500 μm

Figure 5 Polished sections of the fracture specimens. The thickness of the specimen was 3.0 mm, (a): near the surface, (b): half of the thickness.

Figure 6 Fracture appearance of the fracture specimens. The thickness of the specimen was 3.0 mm (↓ indicates notch root).

Figure 7 Fracture surfaces of the fracture specimens. The thickness of the specimen was 3.0 mm; observed points are shown in Fig. 6 (a), (b), and (c).

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7 Continued.

prior to unstable crack growth. As shown in Fig.5, when failure occurs under a mixed mode-type, subcritical crack growth behavior varied with the thickness direction. That is, near the surface, the length of the subcritical crack growth from the root of a notch was larger than that observed at half of the thickness.

The subcritical crack growth at the surface occurred before maximum load. This behavior suggests that the load increased with increasing subcritical crack growth and the fracture toughness increased with the subcritical crack growth from the root of a notch, and suggested that this behavior followed so called "R-curve" behavior.

Fig.6 shows typical fracture appearance of the mixed-mode fractured specimen (the thickness is 3 mm). Detail observations of the fracture surface both stable-fractured and the unstable-fractured parts are shown in Fig.7 (a),(b) and (c) respectively. In the stable fracture parts, (a),(b) in Fig.6, nearly "equiaxed dimples" were formed around carbon fiber and irregular dimple spacing represented that the carbon fiber distribution in the matrix was irregular. Fracture of carbon fibers, both parallel and longitudinal to fiber axis, was observed at the bottom of dimples.

When crack propagated rapidly, the fracture appearance, (c) in Fig.6, was somewhat different from that observed at the subcritical crack growth part, (c). In this part, "elongated dimples" associated with fracture surface in the fracture specimens suggested that the stress state changed during whole failure process of the fracture specimen and the difference of stress state with the thickness of the fracture specimens.

REFERENCES

1. Nakata, E., Kagawa, Y. and Terao, H., Fabrication method of SiC fiber reinforced aluminum and aluminum alloy composites by squeeze casting method. Rep. of the Castings Res. Lab., Waseda Univ., 1983, No.34, 27-36.
2. Kagawa, Y. and Choi, B.H., Tensile strength of Short SiC fiber reinforced aluminum at elevated temperatures. J. Mater. Sci. Lett., (to be contributed).
3. Clyne, T.W., Barder, M.G., Cappleman, G.R. and Hubert, P.A., The use of δ -alumina fiber for metal matrix composites. J. Mater. Sci., 1985, 20, 85-96.
4. Harris, S. and Wilks, T.E., Tensile and fatigue behavior of short alumina fiber reinforced aluminum alloys. Developments in the Science and Technology of Composite Materials, Proc. ECCM, 1985, 595-603.
5. Kagawa, Y., Application of casting technology to fiber reinforced metals, Imono (in Japanese), 1986, 58, 614-621.
6. Liebowitz, H., Subramonian, N., and Lee, J.D., Mechanics of fracture: Fundamentals and some recent developments, Israel J. Tech., Proc. Isr. Annu. Conf., Aviation and Astronautics, 1979, 273-294.
7. Kagawa, Y., and Choi, B.H., Relation between tensile strength and fracture toughness in brittle fiber reinforced metals, Composites'86: Recent Advances in Japan and the United States, Eds. by Kawata, K., Umekawa, S. and Kobayashi, A., 1986, 537-543.

8. Tada, H., The stress analysis of cracks handbook, Del Research Corporation, Hellertown, Pennsylvania, 1973, 2-11.
9. Knott, J. F., Fundamentals of Fracture Mechanics, Butterworth & Co. Ltd, London, 1973, 114